

Mixed Ligand Anionic Complexes of Manganese (II)

Asoke K. Das and D. V. Ramana Rao

An ethanolic solution of manganous chloride is reacted with $R_4N^+Br^-$ ($R = C_2H_5$ or CH_3) to give 2/1 electrolytic complexes of the type $[R_4N]_2 [MnCl_2.Br_2]$. Subsequently these two compounds are reacted separately with different nitrogen donor ligands and several tetra and hexa co-ordinated mixed ligand anionic complexes having the general formulae $[R_4N][MnCl_2.Br.L]$ and $[R_4N][MnCl_2.Br.L_3]$ where L = pyridine, γ -picoline, 3 : 5-lutidine and 4-vinyl pyridine have been isolated. All these complexes have been characterised on the basis of their analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infra-red and electronic spectral data.

Previous work¹⁻⁴ revealed that some transition metal ions form stable four co-ordinated tetrahalo complexes of the type $[MX_4]$. Several tetra, penta and hexa co-ordinated anionic complexes containing hetero donor atoms were also reported⁵⁻⁷. Anionic complexes of manganese (II) containing mixed halogens and their reactions with hetero donor ligands do not appear to have been studied earlier. It was therefore thought worthwhile to investigate these aspects of divalent manganese complexes and we report in this communication a number of four and six co-ordinated anionic complexes of manganese (II) having the general formulae $[R_4N]_2 [MnCl_2.Br_2]$, $[R_4N][MnCl_2.Br.L]$ and $[R_4N][MnCl_2.Br.L_3]$ where L is pyridine (Py), γ -picoline (γ -pic), 3 : 5-lutidine (3 : 5-lut) or 4-vinyl pyridine (4-v.py).

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The starting compounds, $[R_4N]_2 [MnCl_2.Br_2]$ where R is an ethyl or a methyl group, were prepared for the first time by refluxing an alcoholic solution of manganous chloride and the corresponding quaternary bromide in stoichiometric ratio for an hour and then allowing the resulting solution to cool. The mixed ligand anionic complexes were obtained by refluxing $[R_4N]_2 [MnCl_2.Br_2]$ where $R = C_2H_5$ or CH_3 with the ligand (L) taken in different ratios in ethanol or methanol respectively for an hour followed by cooling. Attempts to isolate the complexes having the composition $[Me_4N][MnCl_2.Br.L]$ were unsuccessful.

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All the complexes obtained were suction filtered, washed with ethanol, then with ether and finally dried in *vacuo*. The composition of the complexes was established by estimating the metal and the halogens by standard methods. All the compounds have high melting points and many do not melt or decompose upto 250°. The conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature with $M/1000$ solutions in acetone medium using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined for solid specimens using Gouy method. The relevant analytical, conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in Table 1. The infrared spectra of these complexes both as nujol and hexachloro butadiene mulls were recorded in the region 5000-650 cm^{-1} using Unicam SP 200 double beam spectrophotometer with rock salt optics. Some principal infrared absorption bands of the free ligands and the complexes are recorded in Table 2. The electronic spectra (Table 3) of five complexes in acetonitrile (saturated solutions) were recorded in the visible range using a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer.

TABLE 1

Analysis, Magnetic Susceptibility and Molar Conductance data of Anionic Manganese (II) Complexes

Compound	% Chlorine		% Bromine		% Manganese		Λ_M (mhos)	M_{eff} (B.M.)
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.		
[Et ₃ N] ₂ [MnCl ₂ .Br ₂]	12.86	13.01	29.02	29.28	9.51	10.07	196	5.60
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(Py)]	16.65	17.12	18.79	19.26	12.61	13.24	123	5.85
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(Py) ₃]	12.24	12.40	13.77	13.95	9.13	9.59	84	5.89
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(γ -pic)]	16.00	16.56	18.01	18.63	12.22	12.81	123	5.75
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(γ -pic) ₃]	10.73	11.54	12.10	12.99	8.61	8.93	90	5.92
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(3 : 5-lut)]	15.80	16.03	17.79	18.04	12.00	12.41	111	5.80
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(3 : 5-lut) ₃]	10.36	10.81	11.67	12.16	8.50	8.37	90	5.85
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(4-v.py)]	15.58	16.11	17.52	18.12	12.00	12.47	110	5.70
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(4-v.py) ₃]	10.53	10.91	11.85	12.27	8.10	8.44	88	6.00
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [MnCl ₂ .Br ₂]	16.37	16.37	36.92	36.84	12.33	12.67	204	5.70
[Me ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br[(Py) ₃]	13.58	13.74	15.31	15.46	10.81	10.63	90	5.95
[Me ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(γ -pic) ₃]	12.47	12.71	14.07	14.30	9.33	9.83	103	6.00
[Me ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(3 : 5-lut) ₃]	11.99	11.81	13.50	13.29	8.80	9.14	121	6.01
[Me ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br(4-v.py) ₃]	11.59	11.93	13.05	13.43	9.02	9.23	84	5.88

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Divalent manganese ion has symmetrical half filled 3d⁵ shell which causes least perturbation to the shape whatever may be the preferred stereochemistry of a particular complex. This was known to form either spin free tetrahedral or more common octahedral complexes involving the use of 4s 4p³ or 4s 4p³ 4d² hybrid orbitals for bonding. All the complexes reported in this investigation are spin-free complexes with high magnetic moments ranging between 5.60 and 6.01 B.M. (Table 1) indicating the presence of five unpaired spins.

TABLE 2

*Principal infrared absorption bands (cm⁻¹) of the ligands
(in parentheses) and Manganese (II) complexes.*

Compound	$\nu(\text{C-H})$	$\nu(\text{C} \dots \text{C}) + \nu(\text{C} \dots \text{N})$	(Et ₄ N) ⁺ or (Me ₄ N) ⁺
[Et ₄ N] ₂ [MnCl ₂ .Br ₂]	—	—	1184vs, 795s (1180s, 795s)
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(Py)]	2978m (3040m)	1601vs, 1557s, 1492m (1589s, 1555w, 1486s)	1182vs, 790m
[Et ₄ N] · [MnCl ₂ .Br.(Py) ₃]	2900w	1609s, 1558s, 1520m	1183m, 794m
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(γ -pic)]	3025m (3050m)	1620vs, 1570s, 1513s (1610vs, 1570m, 1498m)	1185vs, 800s
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(γ -pic) ₃]	3000m	1622vs, 1570m, 1508s	1170m, 800s
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .B1.(3 : 5-lut)]	2960s (3008m)	1601s, 1558s, 1545s (1580s, 1542vs, 1508vs)	1180s, 790m
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(3 : 5-lut) ₃]	2920s	1599s, 1555s, 1540s	1170s, 800s
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(4-v.py)]	2940s (3075m)	1611s, 1560s, 1540s (1600vs, 1558s, 1508s)	1180vs, 780s
[Et ₄ N] · [MnCl ₂ .B1.(4-v.py) ₃]	2950w	1608vs, 1558m, 1520s	1165m, 793 vs 950s, 720s (970vs, 745s)
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [MnCl ₂ .Br ₂]	—	—	950s, 720s (970vs, 745s)
[Me ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(Py) ₃]	2930s	1597vs, 1570s, 1506s	950vs, 720w
[Me ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(γ -pic) ₃]	2970m	1620vs, 1560s, 1502m	944vs, 713s
[Me ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(3 : 5-lut) ₃]	2900m	1591s, 1552s, 1532s	942s, 713m
[Me ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(4-v.py) ₃]	2900w	1609s, 1558s, 1520m	944m, 717m

s—strong, vs—very strong, w—weak, m—medium.

TABLE 3

Electronic (visible) spectral data of some manganese (II) complexes.

Compound	$\lambda_{\text{max.}} (\text{cm}^{-1})$
[Et ₄ N] ₂ [MnCl ₂ .Br ₂]	27770, 23810, 22730, 20410
[Me ₄ N] ₂ [MnCl ₂ .Br ₂]	27390, 23920, 22730, 20490
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .Br.(3 : 5-lut)]	* 28570, 25640, 22470, 20640
[Et ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .B1.(Py) ₃]	25000, 22730, 18520, 17240
[Me ₄ N] [MnCl ₂ .B1.(4-v.py) ₃]	27000, 25000, 18520, 16940

The isolated complexes can be grouped under three categories (a) Anionic complexes containing mixed halogens (tetra coordinated), (b) Mixed ligand anionic complexes (tetra coordinated) and (c) Mixed ligand anionic complexes (hexa coordinated).

The first category compounds have the composition $[\text{R}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{MnCl}_2.\text{Br}_2]$ where $\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ or CH_3 as is evident from the analytical data (Table 1). They are light green crystalline compounds having poor solubility in organic solvents. The molar conductance, Λ_M in acetone is round about 200 mhos indicative of 2/1 electrolyte. I.R. spectra also indicate the presence of quaternary halide. Hence these two complexes are tetra coordinated anionic complexes of manganese (II) containing mixed halogens

The compounds having the composition $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{MnCl}_2.\text{Br}.\text{L}]$ where $\text{L} =$ pyridine or a substituted pyridine are light green crystalline compounds and are sparingly soluble in acetone in which medium they are essentially 1/1 electrolytes. Similar tetra coordinated mixed ligand anionic complexes having the formulae $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{MX}_3 \text{Benzimidazole}]$ where M is cobalt (II) and nickel (II) and X is Br^- or I^- were reported by Goodgame *et al*^{8,9}. The anionic complexes of the type $[\text{MX}_3\text{L}]^-$ where $\text{L} =$ pyridine or picoline, $\text{M} = \text{Co(II)}$, Ni(II) or Zn(II) and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- and I^- were also obtained by Brown *et al*¹⁰.

The complexes having the composition $[\text{R}_4\text{N}][\text{MnCl}_2.\text{Br}.\text{L}_3]$ $\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ or CH_3 are light pink crystalline solids and are sparingly soluble in organic solvents. In acetone, they indicate 1/1 electrolytic nature. Earlier Guru and Ramana Rao⁷ reported some penta and hexa coordinated anionic complexes of Zinc (II) containing mixed ligands. More recently Mahapatra and Ramana Rao while carrying out the reaction of halogens with zinc (II) complexes containing nitrogen donor ligands in ethanol medium have isolated¹¹ some penta and hexa coordinated complexes of the types $[\text{ZnCl}_2.\text{Br}_2 (\gamma\text{-pic})_2]^-$, $[\text{ZnCl}_3(\text{Py})_2]^-$ and $[\text{ZnCl}_3(\gamma\text{-pic})_3]^-$. These compounds also have a similar octahedral environment round the manganese (II) ion.

Some significant infrared absorption bands in case of the free ligands and the complexes only are shown in Table 2. The C-H stretching vibration of the pyridines round about 3000 cm^{-1} is shifted to lower frequency in case of the mixed ligand complexes indicating the coordination of the ligand through the nitrogen atom. But the bands due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ in the region $1600\text{-}1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are shifted to higher frequencies probably due to metal ligand π bond. These are in agreement with the earlier observations¹²⁻¹⁴.

The electronic spectra (Table 3) give more useful information regarding the preferred stereochemistry of these complexes. Forster and Goodgame studied¹⁵ the electronic spectra of $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{Mn}(\text{NCO})_4]$ in acetonitrile and assigned the group of three lowest energy bands as $6A_1 \rightarrow 4T_1(\text{G})$ at 20,400, $6A_1 \rightarrow 4T_2(\text{G})$ at 22,400, $6A_1 \rightarrow 4E$, $4A_1(\text{G})$ at 23,300 cm^{-1} by comparing with the electronic spectra of $[\text{MnBr}_4]^-$ reported¹⁶ earlier. However the bands

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obtained by them at 27,500 and 26,000 cm^{-1} could not be assigned definitely. On the basis of their results they suggested a tetrahedral configuration for $[\text{Mn}(\text{NCO})_4]^-$ ion. The bands obtained in case of the four coordinated complexes reported now *viz.*, $[\text{R}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{MnCl}_2.\text{Br}_2]$ where $\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ or CH_3 and $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{MnCl}_2.\text{Br}(3:5\text{-lut})]$ are near about the regions reported by them indicating a tetrahedral stereochemistry. The hexa coordinated complexes *viz.*, $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{MnCl}_2.\text{Br}.\text{Py}_3]$ and $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][\text{MnCl}_2.\text{Br}(4\text{-v.py.})_3]$, in addition, absorb at 17240 and 16940 cm^{-1} respectively. This is in accordance with an earlier observation of Liptay *et al*¹⁷ who recorded the diffuse reflectance spectrum of $\text{MnPy}_4(\text{CNS})_2$ and obtained an absorption band at 16300 cm^{-1} in addition to the bands at 22900 and 27000 cm^{-1} .

A further distinction¹⁸ between octahedral and tetrahedral manganese (II) complexes is that the extinction coefficient values (ϵ) for tetrahedral compounds are nearly 200 times greater than those for octahedral complexes. A similar behaviour is noticed now but exact values for ϵ could not be computed due to poor solubility of the compounds.

The series of tetrahedral and octahedral anionic complexes containing mixed halogens and mixed ligands seems to be reported now for the first time for divalent manganese.

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Department of Chemistry,
Regional Engineering College,
Rourkela.

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